

Synthesis of Isoxazolo (6,7-d) Benz (1,2) Isoxazoles and Furano (6,7-d) Benz (1,2) Isoxazoles.

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Some isoxazolo (6,7-d) benz (1,2) isoxazoles (III) and furano-(6,7-d) benz (1,2) isoxazoles (V) have been synthesised starting from 7-acyl-6-hydroxy benz (1,2) isoxazoles (II). These condensed heterocyclic ring systems in benz (1,2) isoxazole series are synthesized for the first time. The structures of starting materials, 7-acyl-6-hydroxy-benz (1,2) isoxazoles (II) have been confirmed by NMR spectral data. The antimicrobial activity of some of these compounds has also been evaluated.

BENZ(1,2) isoxazoles are known to possess antifungal, antibacterial, antitubercular and analgesic properties¹⁻⁴. A number of benzofurans are also known to possess antidepressive, diuretic and insecticidal properties⁵⁻⁷. It was, therefore, thought that these two moieties together may modify the physiological and biological properties. Moreover, these compounds represent new condensed heterocyclic ring systems.

were obtained. The structures of these compounds(II) were confirmed by NMR spectral data (Table 1) which is discussed later. These *o*-hydroxy-acyl compounds(II) on treatment with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in presence of potassium hydroxide yielded oximes. The oximes were converted into their oxime acetates by acetic anhydride, which on refluxing with dry pyridine afforded isoxazolo (6,7-d) benz(1,2)isoxazoles(V).

SCHEME

The starting materials, 6-hydroxy-3-substituted benz(1,2)-isoxazoles (I, $R_1 = \text{CH}_3$ or CH_2CH_3) were obtained from resacetophenone and respropionophenone by a procedure reported by us earlier⁸. The esters of hydroxy-benz(1,2) isoxazoles were subjected to Fries migration⁹ when 7-acyl-6-hydroxy-benz(1,2)isoxazoles(II)

The hydroxy-acyl benz(1,2) isoxazoles(II) were also converted into furano(6,7-d) benz(1,2) isoxazoles by Kostanecki and Tamber method¹⁰.

The melting points, percentage yields, crystallisation solvents etc. of 6-hydroxy-7-acyl benz(1,2)isoxazoles(II),

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TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND NMR SPECTRAL DATA OF 6-HYDROXY-7-ACYL BENZ (1, 2) ISOXAZOLES (II)

Sr. No.	Compound II*		M.P. °C	Yield %	NMR spectral data (chemical shift in δ)						OH	
	R ₁	R ₂			R ₁		R ₂		Aromatic protons			
	CH ₃	CH ₂			CH ₃	CH ₂	CH ₃	CH ₂	H ^b	H ^a		
1.**	CH ₃	CH ₃	122 ^a	65	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
2.	CH ₃	CH ₂ CH ₃	88 ^b	70	—	2.42 (s)	3.24 (q) J = 7.5Hz	1.20 (t) J = 7.5Hz	6.68 (d) J = 8.5Hz	7.49 (d) J = 8.5Hz	13.33 (s)	
3.	CH ₂ CH ₃	CH ₃	72 ^b	60	2.91 (q) J = 7Hz	1.42 (t) J = 7Hz	—	2.88 (s)	6.36 (d) J = 8Hz	7.62 (d) J = 8Hz	13.28 (s)	
4.	CH ₂ CH ₃	CH ₂ CH ₃	65 ^a	65	2.94 (q) J = 7Hz	1.43 (t) J = 7Hz	3.17 (q) J = 7Hz	1.28 (t) J = 7Hz	6.88 (d) J = 8Hz	7.62 (d) J = 8Hz	13.41 (s)	

* Satisfactory analysis have been obtained for carbon and hydrogen.

** Reported earlier by S. S. Kumari et al.⁹

a : Crystallised from 60% alcohol ; b : Crystallised from 80% alcohol ;

s : singlet ; d : doublet ; t : triplet ; q = quartet.

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL DATA OF INTERMEDIATE OXIMES, OXIME ACETATES AND ISOXAZOLO-(6,7-d) BENZ (1,2) ISOXAZOLES (III)

Sr. No.	Substituents		Intermediates				Isoxazolo (6,7-d)-benz (1,2) isoxazoles(III) ⁹	
	R ₁	R ₂	Oximes		Oxime acetates		M. P. °C	
			M.P. °C	Yield %	M.P. °C	Yield %	M. P. °C	Yield %
1.	CH ₃	CH ₃	214 ^a	90	136 ^d	75	157 ^d	85
2.	CH ₃	CH ₂ CH ₃	184 ^b	85	105 ^d	70	94 ^c	90
3.	CH ₂ CH ₃	CH ₃	170 ^b	85	134 ^d	70	98 ^c	90
4.	CH ₂ CH ₃	CH ₂ CH ₃	146 ^b	75	98 ^d	65	78 ^c	80

* Satisfactory analyses have been obtained for carbon and hydrogen.

a - crystallised from acetic acid ; b - crystallised from 60% alcohol ;

c - crystallised from 50% alcohol ; d - crystallised from alcohol.

TABLE 3—PHYSICAL DATA OF 7-ACYL-6-CARBETHOXY-METHOXY BENZ (1,2) ISOXAZOLES, 7-acyl-6-carboxy-methoxy BENZ (1,2) ISOXAZOLES(IV) AND FURANO-(6,7-d) BENZ (1,2) ISOXAZOLE (V).

Sr. No.	Substituents		Carbethoxy-methoxy-benz (1,2) isoxazole*		Carboxy-methoxy-benz (1,2) isoxazole (IV)*		Furano-(6,7-d) benz (1,2)-isoxazole (V)*	
	R ₁	R ₂	M.P. °C		M.P. °C		M.P. °C	
			M.P. °C	Yield %	M.P. °C	Yield %	M.P. °C	Yield %
1.	CH ₃	CH ₃	105 ^a	75	208 ^b	85	71 ^a	65
2.	CH ₃	CH ₂ CH ₃	118 ^a	70	198 ^a	85	46 ^b	60
3.	CH ₂ CH ₃	CH ₃	98 ^a	80	174 ^a	90	37 ^a	60
4.	CH ₂ CH ₃	CH ₂ CH ₃	112 ^a	70	178 ^a	80	liquid**	50

* Satisfactory analyses have been obtained for carbon and hydrogen.

** Isolated as crude product due to insufficient quantity for further purification.

a - crystallised from 60% alcohol ; b - crystallised from 80% alcohol.

isoxazolo (6,7-d) benz(1,2) isoxazoles(III), furano(6,7-d) benz(1,2)-isoxazoles(V) and their corresponding intermediates are summarised in Tables 1, 2 and 3 respectively.

NMR spectra : The NMR spectra of 6-hydroxy-7-acyl benz(1,2) isoxazoles(II) were scanned on Varian 100 MHz instrument using TMS as an internal standard. The data is summarised in Table 1.

All hydroxy-acyl benz(1,2) isoxazoles(II) showed two doublets in the aromatic region for two ortho phenyl protons ($J = 8\text{Hz}$). This observation confirmed '7' position for the acyl group in these compounds. The down field ($\sim 13.3\delta$) OH proton indicated a strong hydrogen bonding.

Physiological activity : The antibacterial activity of some of these compounds has been evaluated using *M. tuberculosis* and *T. mentagrophytes*. 3-Ethyl-7-acyl-6-hydroxy benz(1,2)isoxazole and 3-ethyl-3'-methyl isoxazolo (6,7-d) benz(1,2) isoxazole showed maximum activity in inhibiting the growth of *M. tuberculosis* at 100 ppm. The former compound is also found to be active against *T. mentagrophytes* at 200 ppm. In addition to this some compounds have been tested also against plant pathogens like, *Phoma herbarum*, *Helminthosporium apatarnae* and *Fusarium* sp. It was found that only 6-hydroxy-7-propionyl-3-methyl benz(1,2) isoxazole showed promising inhibition of growth of the above fungi at 50 ppm.

Experimental

All 6-hydroxy benz(1,2) isoxazoles(I) were prepared according to earlier reported procedures.

General procedures for the preparation of :

(i) **6-Hydroxy-7-acyl benz(1,2) isoxazoles(II) :** A mixture of hydroxy benz(1,2) isoxazole (0.1 mole), acid anhydride (0.12 mole) and pyridine (5 ml) was kept at room temperature for 4 hours and poured over crushed ice containing dilute hydrochloric acid. The acyloxy compound so obtained was crystallised from aqueous alcohol.

A mixture of the ester (0.05 mole) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (0.1 mole) was heated on an oil bath at $135-40^\circ$ for about 2 hours. The resulting complex was decomposed with dilute hydrochloric acid and poured over crushed ice. The solid was dissolved in dilute sodium hydroxide solution and reprecipitated from the solution by acidification and crystallised from aqueous alcohol.

(ii) **Isoxazolo(6,7-d) benz(1,2) isoxazoles(III) :** A mixture of 6-hydroxy-7-acyl benz(1,2) isoxazole (0.01 mole), 40% potassium hydroxide solution (17 ml) and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.045 mole) was stirred, in an ice bath for about 4 hours. The cold, clear solution was neutralised with dilute hydrochloric acid. The resulting oxime was crystallised from aqueous alcohol.

The above oxime (1 g.) was warmed with acetic anhydride (2 ml) till it dissolved and kept at room temperature for 30 minutes and then poured over ice-water. The resulting oxime acetate was crystallised from alcohol.

The above oxime acetate (1g.) was refluxed with dry pyridine (10 ml) for about 3 hours. The resulting reaction mixture was poured on crushed ice containing enough dilute hydrochloric acid to neutralise pyridine. The solid obtained was filtered, washed with dilute sodium hydroxide solution and crystallised from aqueous alcohol.

(iii) **Furano (6,7-d) benz(1,2) isoxazole(V) :** A mixture of the sodium salt of hydroxy-acyl benz(1,2)-isoxazole (0.01 mole) and bromo acetic ester (0.11 mole) was heated on an oil bath at $130-40^\circ$ for 2 hours. The reaction mixture was then poured on ice-water and the resulting carbethoxymethoxy compound was crystallised from aqueous alcohol.

The ester so obtained was heated with 1 N sodium hydroxide on a water bath for 30 minutes. The clear solution so obtained was neutralised with dilute hydrochloric acid. The resulting solid was crystallised from aqueous alcohol.

A mixture of the above phenoxy acetic acid (0.5 g), acetic anhydride (4 ml) and sodium acetate (1 gm) was refluxed on an oil bath at $160-70^\circ$ for about 2 hours. The reaction mixture was then poured over ice. The resulting solid was washed with dilute sodium hydroxide and crystallised from aqueous alcohol.

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